

DRAGONS

Science Quality Verification: Imaging Part 2

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This is the second of a series of articles on the verification of Data Reduction for Astronomy from Gemini Observatory North and South ([DRAGONS](#)), the first public release of which occurred in late 2019. The first article in the series was presented in the inaugural issue of [The Mirror](#). Here we present another example with a different instrument, the Gemini South Adaptive Optics Imager ([GSAOI](#)), and compare with an equivalent Gemini Image Reduction and Analysis Facility (IRAF) reduction for the purpose of demonstrating similar photometric accuracy.

The GSAOI dataset covers three bands (J , H , K_s). For each band, we have 24 raw images, as well as lamp-on and lamp-off dome flat exposures (only lamp-on for the J band). The data are available in the [Gemini Observatory Archive](#). The reductions were done with both DRAGONS and IRAF (using the PyRAF wrapper) in a standard way as described in the [DRAGONS tutorials](#) and the [Gemini IRAF examples](#). DRAGONS and Gemini IRAF do not have the same default parameter options, so it is important to consider certain parameters carefully, as will be shown.

The output units for Gemini IRAF are either Analog to Digital Units (ADUs) (F2, NIRI) or electrons (GMOS, GSAOI), whereas DRAGONS' output is always in electrons. Sources are detected in the stacked images, using DRAGONS' `detectSources` primitive which runs SExtractor [1]. A list of reference sources with magnitudes from the Two Micron All Sky Survey^a (2MASS) catalog is included with the stacked data. The reference catalog is matched to the sources detected in the image and it is used to determine the astrometric solution, and can then be used to measure the magnitude zeropoint. This is very similar to the procedure used by the Quality Assessment Pipeline (QAP, an internal Observatory tool used by observers to assess the data characteristics). Sources without measured instrumental magnitudes or reference magnitudes are removed.

To reduce the science images with PyRAF/IRAF, we use the `skyimg="time"` option to compute the sky image in a way similar to DRAGONS, filtering the current list for images that are within `maxtime=900s` of the image currently being reduced. The parameters `"fl_mult=no"` and `"fl_autosky=no"` are used to keep the values in ADUs and to avoid adding back the median sky level, respectively. The latter parameter choice makes it easier to compare the PyRAF reduced images with DRAGONS.

Finally, for both IRAF and DRAGONS, we correct the distortions and stack the images with [Disco-Stu](#), with the

“--reference” option to use the same World Coordinate System (WCS) for the purpose of the comparison. Before running Disco-Stu, the mean background level was manually subtracted for both the DRAGONS and IRAF reductions. The “skysub” option in Disco-Stu did not work for this data set because at the time, it was not using the object masks and was using a less robust fitting method. This has been fixed and will be available in a future release.

To compare the photometric accuracy of the reductions, we provide two types of plots. Figure 1 compares the measured magnitudes with the reference catalog magnitudes. This plot has fewer sources, because the 2MASS reference catalog does not have many measured objects over the Gemini/GSAOI field. We compute a mean error for the magnitude difference, weighted by the individual magnitude errors. The sources that are excluded from DRAGONS for the reasons mentioned above are also excluded from the IRAF results in order to use the same sources. Figure 2 compares the magnitudes for all the sources that have been detected and matched in the two final images.

With this comparison we have shown that the magnitudes obtained from the stacked images produced using the two software packages are consistent. The mean difference with respect to the reference magnitudes is usually less than 0.05 to 0.1 mag and DRAGONS performs at least as well as IRAF.

DRAGONS has a better handling of bad, non-linear, and saturated pixels, with data-quality flags that are propagated through the reduction and to SExtractor, and then used to exclude these problematic sources. DRAGONS also provides a much faster data processing and a simpler reduction experience compared to IRAF. Further details can be found in the report DRAGONS Science Quality Verification: Imaging^b.

References

[1] Bertin, E. & Arnouts, S. 1996, *A&AS*, 117, 393

Notes

^a This publication makes use of data products from 2MASS, which is a joint project of the University of Massachusetts and the Infrared Processing and Analysis Center/ California Institute of Technology, funded by the National Aeronautics and Space Administration and the National Science Foundation.

^b <http://www.gemini.edu/sciops/data/SUSD/DRAGONSImagingSVReport.pdf>

Figure 1. The top panel plots the magnitude from SExtractor (using the MAG_AUTO parameter that uses an adaptively scaled aperture) versus the 2MASS catalog reference magnitude. The bottom panels show the magnitude difference, MAG_AUTO – REF_MAG, for DRAGONS and IRAF. (Credit: NOIRLab/NSF/AURA/U. Mass/IRAC/Caltech/NASA)

Figure 2. Comparison of DRAGONS and IRAF magnitudes (both from SExtractor MAG_AUTO) for the J (blue), H (green) and Ks (red) bands. (Credit: NOIRLab/NSF/AURA/U. Mass/IRAC/ Caltech/NASA)